

1 **A TETRAAZAHYDROXYPYRIDINONE DERIVATIVE AS INHIBITOR OF APPLE JUICE**
2 **ENZYMATIC BROWNING AND OXIDATION**

3 Sara Muñoz-Pina¹, Aitana Duch-Calabuig¹, José V. Ros-Lis^{2*}, Begoña Verdejo³, Enrique
4 García-España³, Ángel Argüelles¹, Ana Andrés¹

5 ¹ Instituto Universitario de Ingeniería de Alimentos para el Desarrollo (IUIAD-UPV).
6 Universitat Politècnica de València Camino de Vera s/n, 46022, Valencia, Spain.

7 ² REDOLÍ, Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Universitat de València, 46100,
8 Burjassot, Valencia Spain.

9 ³ Instituto de Ciencia Molecular, Universitat de València. C/Catedrático José Beltrán 2,
10 46980, Paterna (Valencia), Spain.

11 *Corresponding author. Email: J.Vicente.Ros@uv.es Tel: +34 963544330, Fax: +34
12 963543929

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14 **ABSTRACT**

15 Enzymatic browning in fruits and vegetables can produce undesirable colour changes
16 and adversely affect the taste, flavour, and nutritional value. This fact poses a challenge
17 to the food industry to apply appropriate inhibitors to control enzymatic browning to
18 maintain food quality. Accordingly, this study aims to evaluate the effect of small
19 mazamacrocyclic compounds modified with a hydroxypyridinone similar to kojic acid on
20 enzymatic browning, total polyphenols and antioxidant activity in apple juice. The
21 results showed how these compounds interact with the tyrosinase enzyme in a complex
22 interaction inhibiting its activity. The hydroxypyridinone attached to the macrocycle (**I1**)
23 was crucial to induce the greatest inhibition, being the most powerful inhibitor. The
24 kinetic studies of **I1** reveal mixed-type inhibition over tyrosinase with an IC₅₀ of 0.30 mM,
25 which was much higher than the calculated IC₅₀ for **I2** and **I3**. Furthermore, **I1** at a

26 concentration of 2.25 mM, significantly reduced the enzymatic browning in fresh apple
27 juice by more than 50% after 1 hour under stirring. Also, it completely stops the decrease
28 in the total phenolic content and delays loss of antioxidant capacity during the first 30
29 minutes.

30

31 **Key words:** PPO, inhibition, macrocyclic polyamines, apple juice, physicochemical
32 properties

33

34 **1. Introduction**

35 Enzymatic browning is induced by mechanical and physical stresses taking place
36 during post-harvest processing and storage in a wide range of products including fruits
37 (e.g., apple, bananas and grapes), vegetables (e.g., potatoes, mushrooms and lettuce)
38 and even seafood (e.g., shrimps, spiny lobsters and crabs) (Aksoy, 2020). It generates
39 not only colour changes, but also adverse effects on taste, flavour, and nutritional value
40 losing polyphenols and antioxidants, among others.

41 Enzymatic browning is one of the main obstacles in the industrialization of some
42 fruit/vegetables products (Es-Safi, Eronique Cheynier, & Moutounet, 2003). Polyphenol
43 oxidase (PPO), which is primarily responsible for the enzymatic browning, is a copper-
44 containing enzyme belonging to the oxidoreductase family. The Enzyme Commission
45 (EC), according to its substrate specificity, has classified them in EC1.14.18.1 (cresolase
46 or tyrosinase) and EC1.10.3.1 (diphenol oxidase or catechol oxidase) (Derardja, Pretzler,
47 Kampatsikas, Barkat, & Rompel, 2019; Moon, Kwon, Lee, & Kim, 2020). In enzymatic
48 browning, PPO catalyses the oxidation of monophenols into o-quinones which is
49 followed by a non-enzymatic polymerization. The polymerization of the quinones gives

50 rise to reddish-brownish pigments called melanonids, which are the reason for colour
51 change (Kanteev, Goldfeder, & Fishman, 2015).

52 Apples (*Malus domestica*) are the third most cultivated fruit worldwide, with a
53 production of around 87 million tons in 2019 (FAOSTAT, 2019), with a significant part of
54 total production meant for apple juice (e.g. in the U.S. IN 2018, it was approximately 12
55 % of the total) (Bortolini et al., 2020). Apple juices are highly susceptible to this
56 deteriorative mechanism since apples contain both active PPO and high polyphenol
57 content (Bondonno, Bondonno, Ward, Hodgson, & Croft, 2017; Martino et al., 2019).

58 Currently, there is an increasing trend to consume fresher and minimally processed
59 foods in a way that preserves the sensory and nutritional properties of raw foods. Colour
60 changes derived from enzymatic browning cause rejection by the consumers, leading to
61 high amounts of food waste and economic losses for the industry. In response, the food
62 industry has developed different methods for the prevention of the enzymatic browning
63 (Muñoz-Pina, Ros-Lis, Argüelles, Martínez-Máñez, & Andrés, 2020). Thermal treatments
64 are the most widely used physical method in the food industry, especially in beverages
65 production. However, it has major drawbacks since it affects the nutritional quality of
66 food, affecting thermosensitive nutrients such as vitamins, carotenoids, and
67 anthocyanins. Other technologies have been explored as an alternative to thermal
68 processing for fruits and vegetables, and especially for apple juice, such as ultra-high-
69 pressure homogenization, high-pressure carbon dioxide, or cold plasma (Tinello & Lante,
70 2018). Nonetheless, its application in the industry is still scarce as they have some
71 limitations such as negative effects on the nutritional quality of products or high cost.

72 Chemical inhibitors offer an interesting alternative due to their lower cost,
73 manageability, and minimal alteration of the bioactive compounds. Among all the
74 possibilities, only sulphites or acidifiers are a real alternative to thermal treatments in
75 the food industry. In the case of acidifiers, such as citric acid and ascorbic acid, they
76 inactivate the PPO by lowering the pH value while acting as a chelator or reducing agent
77 (Zhou et al., 2020). On the other hand, reducing agents like sulphites and their
78 derivatives act as irreversible inhibitors of PPO. Nevertheless, the taste alteration and
79 the allergies in the population (to sulphites, for example) have restricted their use
80 (Iyengar & McEvily, 1992).

81 Therefore, the challenge for the food industry is to apply appropriate inhibitors to
82 control enzymatic browning maintaining the quality and extending shelf life while
83 meeting current consumer needs

84 inhibitors of synthetic origin have been reported to inhibit the ppo. synthetic
85 polyphenols like deoxybenzoins or synthetic isoflavones, thiosemicarbazones, or
86 chalcones have shown effective ppo inhibition. in fact, in some cases, they have shown
87 greater inhibiting power than their natural analogues (Zolghadri et al., 2019).

88 Polyamines like chitosan, a polymer containing several organic groups, has been
89 studied in food science for its potential (Huang, Huang, Huang, & Chen, 2007) and also
90 has demonstrated its effectiveness as inhibitor of enzymatic browning (Sapers, 1992).
91 Furthermore, macrocyclic polyamines have also shown great PPO inhibition depending
92 on the number of amino groups and chemical structure, and additionally are very easy
93 to functionalise or branch with different chemical groups (Muñoz-Pina et al., 2020). On
94 the other hand, kojic acid is very well known as a powerful inhibitor that acts as a

95 reducing agent and as a non-competitive inhibitor, becoming a positive reference when
96 testing new PPO inhibitors (Zolghadri et al., 2019). Based on these key features,
97 therefore, we hypothesize that combining a polyamine with a functional group like kojic
98 acid could be an interesting approach for the development of a new family of PPO
99 inhibitors. Thus, a PPO inhibitor that includes a tetraazamacrocycle modified with a
100 hydroxypyridinone similar to kojic acid has been prepared (**I1**) and its effect on
101 enzymatic browning, total polyphenols and the antioxidant activity of apple juice has
102 been studied.

103

104 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

105 **2.1. Chemicals**

106 Commercial tyrosinase enzyme (2687 U/mg), dopamine hydrochloride, Kojic acid, 1,1-
107 Diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl radical (DPPH) and Folin Ciocalteu reagent (2N) were
108 purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Sodium bisphosphate, disodium
109 phosphate and sodium carbonate were acquired from Scharlau (Sharlab S.L., Spain) and
110 anhydrous sodium acetate from Panreac AppliChem (Panreac AppliChem, Barcelona,
111 Spain). Lastly, methanol (99.9%) was purchased from Honeywell (Honeywell, France).
112 The apple juices used in the tests were obtained in the laboratory by liquefying apples
113 (Golden Delicious variety) obtained in a local store.

114 The inhibitors **I1**, **I2**, and **I3** were synthesised according to known procedures: Verdejo
115 et al., 2007 and López-Martínez et al., 2016.

116 **2.2. Study of enzyme-inhibitor interaction over tyrosinase**

117 The effect of the inhibitors (0.67 mM) over commercial PPO (tyrosinase from
118 mushroom) (93.75 U) was tested in presence of dopamine (2.5 mM) at different pH (4.5,
119 5.5 and 6.5) in a phosphate-acetate buffer of 10 mM (Muñoz-Pina et al., 2020). For each
120 pH, a sample in absence of the inhibitor was used as a control. The dopamine oxidation
121 reaction was followed spectrophotometrically at 420 nm by a DU-730 Life Science
122 UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Beckman Coulter, USA). The assays were done in triplicate
123 at 24 °C, measuring the absorbance each 10 s for 5 min. From the absorption-time
124 curves, the initial speed of the reaction was determined from the slope of the linear
125 stretch of the absorption-time curves. The different slopes were used to compare the
126 inhibitory effect of the tested compounds against the control (see equation 1).

$$127 \quad PPO \text{ inhibition } (\%) = \left(\frac{V_{oi}}{V_{o0}} * 100 \right) \quad (1)$$

128 Where V_{o0} is the control initial rate and V_{oi} is the initial rate obtained for the different
129 samples.

130 **2.3. Enzyme kinetics in model system**

131 To determine the inhibition type for the different compounds, a model system was
132 designed where commercial PPO (tyrosinase from mushroom) was reacted with the
133 inhibitor at pH (5.5) using phosphate-acetate buffer 10mM. A one millilitre solution
134 of varying concentrations of dopamine with a final concentration of 0.08 mM to 2 mM
135 was prepared. Then, 0.50 mL of inhibitor/enzyme mixture was subsequently added. The
136 final concentration of enzyme in the assay was 94 U and two inhibitor concentrations
137 were tested (0.66 and 1.5 mM). Enzyme activity was determined by the formation of
138 dopachrome following the increase in absorbance at 420 nm for 5 min ($\epsilon = 3700 \text{ M}^{-1}$
139 cm^{-1}) in a Spectrophotometer Beckman Coulter DU-730 Life Science UV/Vis (Beckman

140 Coulter, USA). (Vermeer, Higgins, Roman, & Doorn, 2013). Since the enzymatic reaction
141 of polyphenol oxidase follows Michaelis–Menten kinetics (Espín et al., 2000), the type
142 of inhibition was determined by calculating K_m and v_{max} constants using the classical
143 method of Lineweaver-Burk representation as a linearization method (Doran, 1998; M.
144 Fan, Ding, Zhang, Hu, & Gong, 2019)

145 **2.4. Inhibitory effect of enzymatic browning over apple juice**

146 Apple juice from cv. Golden Delicious obtained in the laboratory was selected to verify
147 the effect of the best inhibitor on real samples. The inhibitory effect was measured
148 following the procedure reported by Muñoz-Pina, Ros-Lis, Argüelles, Martínez-Máñez,
149 & Andrés, 2020 with slight modifications. Briefly, two millilitres of an aliquot of the
150 cloudy juice were put in contact with 1 mL of an I1 solution, to get a final concentration
151 of 1.12 mM and 2.25 mM. These blends were kept under agitation (400 rpm) for 60
152 minutes to accelerate the oxidation process and the colour change was measured with
153 a spectrophotometer Minolta CM-3600 d (Konica Minolta, Japan) at 0, 5, 10, 20, 30, and
154 60 min. CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ (CIELAB) colour space which comprises L^* (lightness), a^* (red to
155 green) and b^* (yellow to blue) coordinates were obtained using a D65 illuminant and
156 10° observer as a reference system. The total colour difference (ΔE^*) between the juice
157 at time 0 and treated samples was calculated following the equation (2)

$$158 \quad \Delta E^* = \sqrt{(\Delta L^*)^2 + (\Delta a^*)^2 + (\Delta b^*)^2} \quad (2)$$

159 The colour difference between the initial colour and the samples can be classified as
160 not noticeable (0-0.5), slightly noticeable (0.5-1.5), noticeable (1.5-3.0), well visible (3.0-
161 6.0) and great (6.0-12.0), depending on the value of ΔE_{ab}^* (Xiang et al., 2020).

162 **2.5. Determination of total phenolic content (TPC) and antioxidant activity**

163 Total phenolic content was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method (Andrew L
164 Waterhouse, 2002; Aranibar et al., 2018). Briefly, 10 μL of juice sample (see section 2.4)
165 was diluted into 1.58 mL of deionized water and then mixed well with 100 μL of the
166 Folin-Ciocalteu. After reacting for 3 min, 300 μL of Na_2CO_3 (20% w/v) was added to the
167 mixture and left in the dark for 60 min before measuring the absorbance at 765 nm. A
168 blank with the inhibitors was also measured and subtracted if present. The calibration
169 curve was prepared with standard solutions of gallic acid (from 0 to 500 mg/L) by
170 following the same method. The results were expressed as gallic acid equivalent (GAE)
171 (mg GAE/L).

172 The antioxidant activity of the juices by the DPPH method was determined following
173 the method described by Wu et al. (Wu et al., 2020) with slight modifications. A sample
174 of 10 μL of juice (see section 2.4) was added to 1 mL of methanolic solution of DPPH
175 (100 μM). Then, the mixture was kept in the dark for 30 min and absorbance was
176 measured at 517 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Thermo scientific Helios-zeta,
177 USA). The results were determined based on the standard calibration curve from 0 to
178 200 mg/L of Trolox. The data were expressed as Trolox equivalent (mg Trolox/L). All
179 assays were done in triplicate.

180 **2.6. Software and data analysis**

181 Species distribution curves were calculated with the Hyss2009 software of Hyperquad
182 using the protonation constants published in López-Martínez et al., 2016. Data are
183 reported as mean \pm standard deviation. Statgraphics Centurion XVII software was used
184 to perform the analysis of variance (One-Way ANOVA) and Multiple Range Tests by the

185 LSD procedure (least significant difference) of the Fisher test to identify homogeneous
186 groups. A confidence level of 95% (p-value < 0.05) was used.

187

188 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

189 **3.1 Impact of pH on inhibitor-PPO interaction**

190 As noted above, aza-macrocyclic compounds have proved their efficiency in binding
191 PPO via supramolecular interactions. The central cavity can be branched and/or
192 functionalized to produce a wide variety of new compounds with different chemical
193 properties enhancing their supramolecular interactions. 6-[2'-(3'-hydroxy-2''-methyl-4'-
194 pyridinone)ethyl]-3,6,9-triaza-1(2,6)-pyridinacyclodecaphane (**11**) was synthesised as a
195 model by a combination of a hydroxy pyridinone group (similar to kojic acid) with a
196 tetraazamacrocycle. To better understand the influence of the chemical structure on the
197 inhibitor activity, also the related compounds 3,6,9-triaza-1(2,6)-
198 pyridinacyclodecaphane (**13**) and 2-(3,6,9-triaza-1(2,6)-pyridinacyclodecaphane-6-
199 yl)ethan-1-amine (**12**) were synthesised. (see scheme 1).

200 As a first approach, to analyse their inhibitory power, a preliminary screening was
201 carried out in the pH range where PPO is active (4.5, 5.5, 6.5). The pHs were selected
202 considering that the behaviour of polyamines is pH-dependent and most of the fruits
203 that show enzymatic browning present a pH in this range.

204 In general terms, all the tested substances reduce the initial reaction rate, which can
205 be translated as a partial inhibition of the enzymatic activity. The degree of inhibition
206 varies strongly among the assays with a decrease in the initial PPO rate from 20 to 85%
207 depending on the pH and the inhibitor (Figure 1). Initially, the unfunctionalized

208 macrocycle (**I3**) reduces the PPO activity but to a lesser extent than the other inhibitors.
209 The effect decreases as the pH increases reaching 20% at pH 6.5. Similar behaviour is
210 reported by **I2**, however, the extra alkyl amino chain enhances its inhibitory power,
211 especially at pH 4.5 showing a 40% of inhibition. Finally, it is noticeable how the presence
212 of the 3-hydroxy-4-pyridinone functional group (similar to kojic acid) in **I1** increases the
213 inhibition, inducing the greatest inhibition among the inhibitors. At pH 5.5 and 6.5, it
214 reaches an almost complete PPO inhibition (85%) but at low pH, the inhibition slightly
215 decreases (72%).

216 Taking into account that the tested inhibitors can be present as diverse species
217 depending on the pH, the distribution diagram of species at the studied pH range can be
218 found in Figure 2 (Verdejo et al., 2007). **I1**, **I2** and **I3** share the tetraaza macrocycle unit
219 that contains two protonated amino groups—at slightly acidic pH because the third
220 protonation needs very acidic conditions due to electrostatic repulsions with the other
221 cationic groups.—The 3-hydroxypyridinone unit is able to lose one proton at basic pH,
222 thus it is neutral under the pH of study. In the 4.5 - 6.5 pH range, the main species are
223 $[H_2I1]^{2+}$, $[H_3I2]^{3+}$ and $[H_2I3]^{2+}$.

224 Since the isoelectric point of PPO is placed around pH 4.5-5 (Y. Fan & Flurkey, 2004)
225 certain repulsion between the PPO and the positive charges could be expected in
226 particular at pH 4.5. For **I2** and **I3** the percentage of PPO inhibition increases as the pH
227 moves from 6.5 to 4.5, and **I2**, with an additional positive charge (+3) offers a slightly
228 stronger degree of inhibition than **I3**. On the contrary, at pH 6.5 a lower concentration
229 of the partially protonated compounds $[HI1]^+$, $[H_2I2]^{2+}$ and $[HI3]^+$ is present, which could
230 explain the slight reduction of inhibition found for **I2** and **I3** at this pH. These results

231 suggest that the molecule interacts with the enzyme through complex interactions. In
232 accordance with the behaviour observed for similar systems based on cyclic polyamines,
233 an increase in the number of nitrogens improves the inhibition activity (Muñoz-Pina et
234 al., 2020). In any case, the most remarkable observation is that the pyrone group present
235 in **I1** quadruples the inhibitory activity (an 85% in comparison with the 21% of **I3** at pH
236 6.5). However, the macrocyclic cavity, although to a lesser degree compared to the
237 pyrone, also exhibits an inhibitory effect.

238 Taking into account these results, and in order to get a deeper insight, the pH 5.5 was
239 selected for further testing as PPO still had high activity (around 85%) (Munjal &
240 Sawhney, 2002) but was close to or similar to the pH found in some fruit juices like
241 banana or pear (Bora, Handique, & Sit, 2017; Saeeduddin et al., 2017).

242 **3.3. Inhibition mechanisms of aza-macrocyclic compounds.**

243 The classical method of the Lineweaver-Burk plot was used to determine the kinetic
244 parameters to identify the inhibition mechanism of each inhibitor (see Table 1).

245 The kinetics parameters for the control were, in the case of Michaelis-Menten
246 constant, $K_m = 1.52 \text{ mM}$ and 0.26 mM min^{-1} for v_{max} . As expected, the v_{max} reaction rate
247 of the PPO was drastically reduced in the presence of high concentrations of **I1** (0.0157
248 mM min^{-1}) achieving almost a total inhibition. In addition, the Michaelis-Menten
249 constant values progressively decreased as the inhibitor concentration increased with
250 statistically significant differences with respect to the control. Therefore, as the inhibitor
251 favors binding to the enzyme-substrate complex, the observed inhibition can be
252 considered a mixed type non-competitive-uncompetitive inhibition (Palmer & Bonner,
253 2011). The catalytic constant (K_{cat}) and the catalytic efficiency (K_{cat}/K_m) of the enzyme

254 also plummeted from values close to 1000 to values below 250 for both constants. In
255 fact, the catalytic constant drops 94 % when the concentration of **I1** in the medium is
256 1.5 mM, which implies that the efficiency of the enzyme is much lower in its presence.

257 Same v_{\max} and K_m parameters were found (without statistical differences) for **I2** at
258 double concentration (1.50 mM) compared to those found for **I1** at 0.65 mM. Although
259 the type of inhibition is assumed to be the same (mixed type), it appears that the pyrone
260 group offers additional inhibition power that the amine group cannot perform (see
261 Table 1). However, **I2** also achieves a high inhibition on the PPO in the concentrations
262 studied since it manages to reduce the catalytic constant of the enzyme (1350 min^{-1}) to
263 almost half when the concentration is 0.67 mM.

264 However, the last compound, **I3**, behaves differently, exhibiting a non-competitive
265 inhibition on the PPO enzyme. The Michaelis–Menten constant maintains the control
266 values when altering the inhibition concentration, but the v_{\max} drops off. Contrasted
267 with the other two inhibitors, **I3** is not capable of a strong inhibition on the PPO, being
268 necessary to double the concentration to produce an equal K_{cat} as **I2**.

269 Besides, the IC_{50} parameter for **I2** and **I3** is much higher than for **I1** which was
270 calculated at 0.30 mM. In previous studies it was observed how the molecules that
271 presented the same central ring inhibited the PPO enzyme to a lesser extent, making it
272 necessary to increase the central cavity to improve the IC_{50} to around 0.30 mM. However
273 when the central cavity is functionalized with the group similar to kojic acid, the IC_{50}
274 rose to 0.30 mM (Muñoz-Pina et al., 2020). However, this value cannot reach the IC_{50}
275 values obtained for either kojic acid (0.011 mM) or other azamacrocyclic ligands under
276 the same conditions (Muñoz-Pina et al., 2020). Nevertheless, this IC_{50} value of the ligand

277 is substantially better than the value found for other commonly used organic acids found
278 in literature, such as citric acid (20 mM), cinnamic (2.10 mM), or benzoic acid (5.2 mM)
279 (W. Liu et al., 2013; Öz, Colak, Özel, Sağlam Ertunga, & Sesli, 2013; Shi, Chen, Wang,
280 Song, & Qiu, 2005)

281

282 **3.4. Browning inhibition of I1 on apple juice**

283 Considering the positive results obtained for **i1** in model system studies with ppo, we
284 further studied its anti-browning ability in fresh apple juice as a real food system. it is
285 also important to note that preliminary studies of **i1** with two cell lines, hela and arpe-
286 19, do not reveal any toxicity (López-martínez et al., 2016). the liquified juice was mixed
287 with two different concentrations of **I1** (1.12 mM and 2.25 mM) and the colour change
288 was followed over time. Figure 3 shows the colour differences (ΔE_{ab}^*) using the initial
289 colour as reference.

290 Once the apples are liquified, the enzymatic browning process begins rapidly, and the
291 colour change of the control (in absence of inhibitor) is well visible visible to the human
292 eye in 5 minutes ($\Delta E_{ab}^* = 3$). However, in the presence of the inhibitor at 2.25 mM the
293 colour changes are not noticeable. At a lower concentration (1.12 mM), the inhibitor
294 delayed the enzymatic browning, reaching a notable change of colour with a ΔE_{ab}^* close
295 to 2.5 at 10 minutes, similar to the control at 5 min.

296 Even though the speed of PPO decreased in presence of the inhibitor, the enzymatic
297 browning reaction did not stop completely. The colour change in the juice treated with
298 the lowest **I1** concentration (1.12 mM) varies among the 40 and 65% when compared to
299 the untreated sample at the same time. By raising the inhibitor concentration in the

300 juice to 2.25 mM, the enzymatic browning is further delayed with a ΔE_{ab}^* of 0.6 after 10
301 min of stirring compared to 6.0 found for the control. The threshold of colour change to
302 be qualified as “great” is passed within 10 minutes in absence of inhibitor and 60 min at
303 1.12 mM. However, it is not reached if a [I1] = 2.25 mM is used even after 1 hour of
304 exposition to the air under stirring. When measuring the initial browning rate, values for
305 the slope of 0.601, 0.219 and 0.084 $\Delta E_{ab}^* \text{ min}^{-1}$ were calculated for the control and the
306 juices containing 1.12 mM and 2.25 mM respectively ($R^2 > 0.95$). Therefore, reductions
307 in the initial enzymatic browning rate of 86% can be observed in presence of [I1] equal
308 to 2.25 mM.

309

310 **3.5. Effect of I1 on total phenolic content (TPC) and antioxidant capacity (DPPH)** 311 **on apple juice**

312 Apple and their juices contain high concentrations of diverse phenolic compounds
313 such as chlorogenic acid, gallic acid, catechin and quercetin, which are well known for
314 their beneficial effects on human health (Barreira, Arraibi, & Ferreira, 2019). Thus, the
315 effect of the inhibitor over total phenolic content and antioxidant capacity (DPPH) was
316 measured.

317 As shown in figure 4, the initial content of total phenols was about 600 mg of GAE L⁻¹
318 just after liquefying the apple which is in agreement with the range presented in the
319 literature for the same apple variety (Sauceda-Gálvez et al., 2020; Suárez-Jacobo et al.,
320 2011). However, this value decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) as time progressively
321 evolved, reducing the content of phenols by almost 40% after 60 min of stirring. This
322 trend was repeated when the samples were treated with 1.12 mM inhibitor, however,

323 the degradation rate of phenol was slowed down and only 15% was lost after 60
324 minutes. Nonetheless, the decrease in the total phenolic content in the apple juice
325 stopped and remained stable after 60 min in the presence of 2.25 mM of **I1** ($p < 0.05$).
326 The results also showed a good negative correlation (-0.756) between the TPC and
327 enzymatic browning (ΔE_{ab}^*) for $p < 0.05$, as expected from the oxidation of phenolic
328 compounds used as PPO substrates (Persic, Mikulic-Petkovsek, Slatnar, & Veberic,
329 2017). This correlation is stronger for the control (-0.926) than for the juices containing
330 inhibitor (-0.636 for 1.12 mM and -0.266 for 2.25 mM), suggesting that the PPO
331 inhibition induced by **I1** could be more intense than we can deduce from the enzymatic
332 browning.

333 The antioxidant capacity measured with DPPH can be found in Figure 5. As time
334 increases and oxidation occurs, the antioxidant activity of fresh, cloudy apple juice
335 significantly decreases. When **I1** is added, even though after 20 and 30 minutes this
336 effect is significantly diminished, at longer times the loss of radical scavenging species is
337 comparable to the control.

338 According to Pearson's correlations, the reduction of antioxidant properties
339 expressed by the DPPH method is significantly correlated with the enzymatic browning
340 for the control (-0.931) and both concentrations of inhibitor (-0.871 for 1.12 mM and -
341 0.906 for 2.25 mM). However, if we analyse the correlation with the total phenolic
342 content in the presence of 2.25 mM of **I1**, no significant correlation is found ($0.139 > p >$
343 0.05). This behaviour can be explained considering that the DPPH test measures not
344 only phenols but also other compounds present in the apple juice such as vitamins
345 (vitamin C and E), heteropolysaccharides and polypeptides (D. Liu, Shi, Colina Ibarra,

346 Kakuda, & Jun Xue, 2008; X. X. Liu et al., 2020). Similar results were found on fresh
347 lettuce when testing citric acid and oxalic acid as inhibitors, where no correlation was
348 found between antioxidant activity and total phenolic content in the presence of the
349 inhibitors (Altunkaya & Gökmen, 2008). Also, in a recently published article (Wu et al.,
350 2020) the authors correlated the content of nine different phenolic compounds found
351 in apple juice and the antioxidant activity determined by the DPPH method. The study
352 showed how significant positive correlations were only obtained for the content of
353 caffeic acid and phlorizin for $p < 0.05$ (0.677 and 0.532 respectively). Although no
354 correlation was found for chlorogenic acid or epicatechin, which were the most
355 abundant phenolic compound besides the phlorizin in apple juice. Thus, the oxidation
356 process in the presence of **I1** could damage more polyphenols such as caffeic acid, which
357 have a greater impact on the antioxidant activity than TPC..

358

359 **4. CONCLUSION**

360 The effect on the PPO enzyme of three different azamacrocyclic inhibitors has been
361 tested. The inhibition studies at different pHs suggest that the interaction with the PPO
362 enzyme is not due to electrostatic forces but through other complex interactions.
363 Furthermore, the presence of hydroxypyridinone attached to the macrocycle was
364 relevant to enhance the inhibitor power especially at pH 5.5 and 6.5. Kinetic studies
365 denote a mixed type of inhibition of **I1** with an IC_{50} (0.30 mM) much higher than the one
366 calculated for **I2** and **I3**. The inhibitory activity of **I1** was validated on freshly obtained
367 apple juice as a real food system. The inhibitor can reduce the enzymatic browning by
368 more than 50% and the decrease in total phenolic content in apple juice was stopped

369 when used 2.25 mM. Furthermore, **I1** delays, at least during the first 30 min, the
370 antioxidant capacity measured with DPPH.

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375 102331-T, PID 2019-110751RD-I00 and Unidad de Excelencia CEX2019-000919-M).

376 **References**

377 Aksoy, M. (2020). A new insight into purification of polyphenol oxidase and inhibition
378 effect of curcumin and quercetin on potato polyphenol oxidase. *Protein*
379 *Expression and Purification*, 171, 105612.

380 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pep.2020.105612>

381 Altunkaya, A., & Gökmen, V. (2008). Effect of various inhibitors on enzymatic
382 browning, antioxidant activity and total phenol content of fresh lettuce (*Lactuca*
383 *sativa*). *Food Chemistry*, 107(3), 1173–1179.

384 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2007.09.046>

385 Andrew L Waterhouse. (2002). Determination of total phenolics. In *Current protocols in*
386 *food analytical chemistry* (1st ed., Vol. 6, p. I1.1.1-I1.1.8). John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

387 Aranibar, C., Pigni, N. B., Martinez, M., Aguirre, A., Ribotta, P., Wunderlin, D., &
388 Borneo, R. (2018). Utilization of a partially-deoiled chia flour to improve the
389 nutritional and antioxidant properties of wheat pasta. *LWT - Food Science and*
390 *Technology*, 89, 381–387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2017.11.003>

391 Barreira, J. C. M., Arraibi, A. A., & Ferreira, I. C. F. R. (2019, August 1). Bioactive and

392 functional compounds in apple pomace from juice and cider manufacturing:
393 Potential use in dermal formulations. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*.
394 Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2019.05.014>

395 Bondonno, N. P., Bondonno, C. P., Ward, N. C., Hodgson, J. M., & Croft, K. D. (2017,
396 November 1). The cardiovascular health benefits of apples: Whole fruit vs.
397 isolated compounds. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*. Elsevier Ltd.
398 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2017.04.012>

399 Bora, S. J., Handique, J., & Sit, N. (2017). Effect of ultrasound and enzymatic pre-
400 treatment on yield and properties of banana juice. *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry*, *37*,
401 445–451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ULTSONCH.2017.01.039>

402 Bortolini, D. G., Benvenuti, L., Demiate, I. M., Nogueira, A., Alberti, A., & Zielinski, A. A.
403 F. (2020). A new approach to the use of apple pomace in cider making for the
404 recovery of phenolic compounds. *LWT*, *126*, 109316.
405 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2020.109316>

406 Derardja, A. eddine, Pretzler, M., Kampatsikas, I., Barkat, M., & Rompel, A. (2019).
407 Inhibition of apricot polyphenol oxidase by combinations of plant proteases and
408 ascorbic acid. *Food Chemistry: X*, *4*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fochx.2019.100053>

409 Doran, P. M. (1998). *Principios de ingeniería de los bioprocesos*. Acribia.

410 Es-Safi, N.-E., Eronique Cheynier, V., & Moutounet, M. (2003). Implication of phenolic
411 reactions in food organoleptic properties. *Journal of Food Composition and*
412 *Analysis*, *16*, 535–553. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-1575\(03\)00019-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-1575(03)00019-X)

413 Espín, J. C., Varón, R., Fenoll, L. G., Gilabert, M. A., García-Ruíz, P. A., Tudela, J., &
414 García-Cánovas, F. (2000). Kinetic characterization of the substrate specificity and
415 mechanism of mushroom tyrosinase. *European Journal of Biochemistry*, *267*(5),

416 1270–1279. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1432-1327.2000.01013.x>

417 Fan, M., Ding, H., Zhang, G., Hu, X., & Gong, D. (2019). Relationships of dietary
418 flavonoid structure with its tyrosinase inhibitory activity and affinity. *LWT*, *107*,
419 25–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LWT.2019.02.076>

420 Fan, Y., & Flurkey, W. H. (2004). Purification and characterization of tyrosinase from gill
421 tissue of Portabella mushrooms. *Phytochemistry*, *65*(6), 671–678.
422 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2004.01.008>

423 Huang, J. ru, Huang, C. yi, Huang, Y. wen, & Chen, R. hui. (2007). Shelf-life of fresh
424 noodles as affected by chitosan and its Maillard reaction products. *LWT - Food
425 Science and Technology*, *40*(7), 1287–1291.
426 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LWT.2006.08.004>

427 Iyengar, R., & McEvily, A. J. (1992). Anti-browning agents: alternatives to the use of
428 sulfites in foods. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, *3*, 60–64.
429 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0924-2244\(92\)90131-F](https://doi.org/10.1016/0924-2244(92)90131-F)

430 Kanteev, M., Goldfeder, M., & Fishman, A. (2015). Structure-function correlations in
431 tyrosinases. *Protein Science : A Publication of the Protein Society*, *24*(9), 1360–
432 1369. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.2734>

433 Liu, D., Shi, J., Colina Ibarra, A., Kakuda, Y., & Jun Xue, S. (2008). The scavenging
434 capacity and synergistic effects of lycopene, vitamin E, vitamin C, and β -carotene
435 mixtures on the DPPH free radical. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, *41*(7),
436 1344–1349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2007.08.001>

437 Liu, W., Zou, L., Liu, J., Zhang, Z., Liu, C., & Liang, R. (2013). The effect of citric acid on
438 the activity, thermodynamics and conformation of mushroom polyphenoloxidase.
439 *Food Chemistry*, *140*(1–2), 289–295.

440 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2013.02.028>

441 Liu, X. X., Liu, H. M., Yan, Y. Y., Fan, L. Y., Yang, J. N., Wang, X. De, & Qin, G. Y. (2020).
442 Structural characterization and antioxidant activity of polysaccharides extracted
443 from jujube using subcritical water. *LWT*, *117*, 108645.
444 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2019.108645>

445 López-Martínez, L. M., Pitarch-Jarque, J., Martínez-Camarena, À., García-España, E.,
446 Tejero, R., Santacruz-Ortega, H., ... Verdejo, B. (2016). Synthesis, Characterization,
447 and Cu²⁺ Coordination Studies of a 3-Hydroxy-4-pyridinone Aza Scorpiand
448 Derivative. *Inorganic Chemistry*, *55*(15), 7564–7575.
449 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.6b01006>

450 Martino, E., Vuoso, D. C., D'Angelo, S., Mele, L., D'Onofrio, N., Porcelli, M., &
451 Cacciapuoti, G. (2019). Annurca apple polyphenol extract selectively kills MDA-
452 MB-231 cells through ROS generation, sustained JNK activation and cell growth
453 and survival inhibition. *Scientific Reports*, *9*(1), 1–15.
454 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-49631-x>

455 Moon, K. M., Kwon, E. Bin, Lee, B., & Kim, C. Y. (2020). Recent Trends in Controlling the
456 Enzymatic Browning of Fruit and Vegetable Products. *Molecules*, *25*(12).
457 <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25122754>

458 Munjal, N., & Sawhney, S. . (2002). Stability and properties of mushroom tyrosinase
459 entrapped in alginate, polyacrylamide and gelatin gels. *Enzyme and Microbial
460 Technology*, *30*(5), 613–619. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0229\(02\)00019-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0229(02)00019-4)

461 Muñoz-Pina, S., Ros-Lis, J. V., Argüelles, Á., Martínez-Máñez, R., & Andrés, A. (2020).
462 Influence of the functionalisation of mesoporous silica material UVM-7 on
463 polyphenol oxidase enzyme capture and enzymatic browning. *Food Chemistry*,

464 310, 125741. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2019.125741>

465 Muñoz-Pina, S., Ros-Lis, J. V., Delgado-Pinar, E. A., Martı Nez-Camarena, A., Verdejo, B.,
466 Garcı A-España, E., ... Andrés, A. (2020). Inhibitory Effect of Azamacrocyclic
467 Ligands on Polyphenol Oxidase in Model and Food Systems. *Journal of Agricultural
468 and Food Chemistry*, 68(30), 7964–7973.
469 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.0c02407>

470 Öz, F., Colak, A., Özel, A., Sağlam Ertunga, N., & Sesli, E. (2013). Purification And
471 Characterization Of A Mushroom Polyphenol Oxidase And Its Activity In Organic
472 Solvents. *Journal of Food Biochemistry*, 37(1), 36–44.
473 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-4514.2011.00604.x>

474 Palmer, T., & Bonner, P. L. (2011). Enzyme Inhibition. In *Enzymes* (pp. 126–152).
475 Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1533/9780857099921.2.126>

476 Persic, M., Mikulic-Petkovsek, M., Slatnar, A., & Veberic, R. (2017). Chemical
477 composition of apple fruit, juice and pomace and the correlation between
478 phenolic content, enzymatic activity and browning. *LWT - Food Science and
479 Technology*, 82, 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LWT.2017.04.017>

480 Saeeduddin, M., Abid, M., Jabbar, S., Wu, T., Yuan, Q., Riaz, A., ... Zeng, X. (2017).
481 Nutritional, microbial and physicochemical changes in pear juice under ultrasound
482 and commercial pasteurization during storage. *Journal of Food Processing and
483 Preservation*, 41(6), e13237. <https://doi.org/10.1111/JFPP.13237>

484 Sapers, G. M. (1992). Chitosan Enhances Control of Enzymatic Browning in Apple and
485 Pear Juice by Filtration. *Journal of Food Science*, 57(5), 1192–1193.
486 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.1992.tb11296.x>

487 Saucedo-Gálvez, J. N., Codina-Torrella, I., Martínez-García, M., Hernández-Herrero, M.

488 M., Gervilla, R., & Roig-Sagués, A. X. (2020). Combined effects of ultra-high
489 pressure homogenization and short-wave ultraviolet radiation on the properties
490 of cloudy apple juice. *LWT*, *136*, 110286.
491 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2020.110286>

492 Shi, Y., Chen, Q. X., Wang, Q., Song, K. K., & Qiu, L. (2005). Inhibitory effects of
493 cinnamic acid and its derivatives on the diphenolase activity of mushroom
494 (*Agaricus bisporus*) tyrosinase. *Food Chemistry*, *92*(4), 707–712.
495 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2004.08.031>

496 Suárez-Jacobo, Á., Rüfer, C. E., Gervilla, R., Guamis, B., Roig-Sagués, A. X., & Saldo, J.
497 (2011). Influence of ultra-high pressure homogenisation on antioxidant capacity,
498 polyphenol and vitamin content of clear apple juice. *Food Chemistry*, *127*(2), 447–
499 454. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2010.12.152>

500 Tinello, F., & Lante, A. (2018). Recent advances in controlling polyphenol oxidase
501 activity of fruit and vegetable products. *Innovative Food Science and Emerging
502 Technologies*, *50*, 73–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifset.2018.10.008>

503 Verdejo, B., Ferrer, A., Blasco, S., Castillo, C. E., González, J., Latorre, J., ... García-
504 España, E. (2007). Hydrogen and copper ion-induced molecular reorganizations in
505 scorpionand-like ligands. A potentiometric, mechanistic, and solid-state study.
506 *Inorganic Chemistry*, *46*(14), 5707–5719. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ic700643n>

507 Vermeer, L. M., Higgins, C. A., Roman, D. L., & Doorn, J. A. (2013). Real-time monitoring
508 of tyrosine hydroxylase activity using a plate reader assay. *Analytical
509 Biochemistry*, *432*(1), 11–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ab.2012.09.005>

510 Wu, C., Li, T., Qi, J., Jiang, T., Xu, H., & Lei, H. (2020). Effects of lactic acid fermentation-
511 based biotransformation on phenolic profiles, antioxidant capacity and flavor

512 volatiles of apple juice. *LWT*, 122, 109064.
513 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2020.109064>

514 Xiang, Q., Fan, L., Zhang, R., Ma, Y., Liu, S., & Bai, Y. (2020). Effect of UVC light-emitting
515 diodes on apple juice: Inactivation of *Zygosaccharomyces rouxii* and
516 determination of quality. *Food Control*, 111, 107082.
517 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2019.107082>

518 Zhou, L., Liao, T., Liu, W., Zou, L., Liu, C., & Terefe, N. S. (2020). Inhibitory effects of
519 organic acids on polyphenol oxidase: From model systems to food systems.
520 *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 60(21), 3594–3621.
521 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2019.1702500>

522 Zolghadri, S., Bahrami, A., Hassan Khan, M. T., Munoz-Munoz, J., Garcia-Molina, F.,
523 Garcia-Canovas, F., & Saboury, A. A. (2019). A comprehensive review on
524 tyrosinase inhibitors. *Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry*, 34(1),
525 279–309. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14756366.2018.1545767>

526
527

528 **Table captions**

529 **Table 1:** Kinetic parameters and type of inhibition of the enzyme tyrosinase (94 U) in
530 presence of the inhibitors at different concentrations.

531

532 **Figure captions**

533 **Scheme 1.** Molecular structures of the inhibitors **I1**, **I2**, **I3** and kojic acid.

534 **Figure 1.** Polyphenol oxidase (94 U) inhibition in presence of the three different aza-
535 macrocyclic inhibitors (0.67 mM) using dopamine as substrate (2.5 mM) at different pH:
536 4.5 (black), 5.5 (grey) and 6.5 (light grey). A-C: different letters indicate significant
537 differences in PPO inhibition between pH. a-c: different letters indicate significant
538 differences between inhibitors ($p < 0.05$).

539 **Figure 2.** Species distribution curves calculated for the aqueous solution of the inhibitor.
540 Percentage represents concentrations relative to the total amount of inhibitor at an
541 initial value of 0.67 mM.

542 **Figure 3.** Colour changes in apple juice of control (black), in presence of 1.12 mM of **I1**
543 (grey) and 2.25 mM of **I1** (light grey) over time. A-C: different letters indicate significant
544 differences in ΔE_{ab}^* between **I1** concentrations. a-c: different letters indicate significant
545 differences between times ($p < 0.05$). Inset: Colour evolution in apple smoothie followed
546 by images after 60 min. First the control, and then the sample treated with 1.12 mM and
547 2.25 mM of **I1** respectively.

548 **Figure 4.** Total phenol content of apple juice of control (black), in presence of 1.12 mM
549 of **I1** (grey) and 2.25 mM of **I1** (light grey) during the time. A-C: different letters indicate
550 significant differences in total polyphenols between concentrations. a-c: different
551 letters indicate significant differences between times ($p < 0.05$).

552 **Figure 5.** Antioxidant activity (DPPH) of apple juice of control (black), in presence of 1.12
553 mM of **I1** (grey) and 2.25 mM of **I1** (light grey) during the time. A-C: different letters
554 indicate significant differences in DPPH between **I1** concentrations. a-c: different letters
555 indicate significant differences between times ($p < 0.05$).

556 **Table 1**

Compound (mM)	K_M^a (mM)	v_{max}^b (mM min ⁻¹)	k_{cat}^c (min ⁻¹)	Catalytic efficiency ^d (mM ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	IC ₅₀ (mM)	Inhibition type	
Control	1.52* ± 0.09	0.259 ± 0.014	1350 ± 80	888 ± 108			
I1	0.67	1.02* [§] ± 0.07	0.064* ± 0.003	329 ± 14	320 ± 40	0.30 ± 0.05 (0.18 mg/mL)	Mixed type
	1.50	0.33 ± 0.03	0.0157 ± 0.0008	81 ± 4	250 ± 30		
I2	0.67	1.35* [§] ± 0.19	0.151* ± 0.008	780 ± 40	577 ± 108	0.79 ± 0.06 (0.45 mg/mL)	Mixed type
	1.50	0.77 [§] ± 0.08	0.035* ± 0.003	178 ± 16	230 ± 50		
I3	0.67	1.85* ± 0.08	0.222 ± 0.008	1140 ± 50	620 ± 50	1.82 ± 0.16 (0.81mg/mL)	Non-competitive
	1.50	1.7* [§] ± 0.2	0.151* ± 0.019	784 ± 108	460 ± 140		

557 The enzyme (tyrosinase from mushroom) was constant for all assays (94U) ^a Michaelis-Menten constant. ^b Reaction

558 rate. ^c Catalytic constant, $k_{cat}=v_{max}/[E]$. ^d Catalytic efficiency, calculated by k_{cat}/K_M . *[§] There are no statistically

559 significant differences for $p < 0.05$ between rows for K_M or v_{max} . I1 refers to the ligand 6-[2'-(3'-hydroxy-2''-methyl-4'-

560 pyridinone)ethyl]-3,6,9-triaza-1(2,6)-pyridinacyclodecaphane; I2 concern to the compound 2-(3,6,9-triaza-1(2,6)-

561 pyridinacyclodecaphane-6-yl)ethan-1-amine and I3 is the compounds 3,6,9-triaza-1(2,6)-pyridinacyclodecaphane.

562

563 **Scheme 1**

I1

I2

I3

Kojic acid

564

565

566 **Figure 1**

567

568

569

570 **Figure 2**

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573 **Figure 3**

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576 **Figure 4**

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579 **Figure 5**

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